

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF VANADIUM IN NATURAL SAMPLES BY THE PROPOSED METHOD

Sample	Volume taken ml	V found ppb	V added μg	V found ppb
Distilled water	500	*	5.0	9
Tap water	500	*	10.0	19
			5.0	9
			10.0	19
Water sample			10.0	59
JDF/7/26	500	41	20.0	77
JDF/8/32	250	472.8		
	500	468.6		
JDF/8/3	250	33.5		
	500	35.5		
BSL/21	500	<10		
	500	<10		
MJN/1/3	250	130		
	500	128		
Rock sample	% V_2O_5	0.022		
BSL-16/11		(0.021)%		
BSL-16/12	% V_2O_5	0.020		
		(0.019)%		

*Not detectable.

Values within the parenthesis were obtained by BPHA method².

beyond which the extraction of vanadium falls. Mixture of chloroform and butanol (4:1) was found to be the best compromise to obtain optimum sensitivity and stability. Large amounts (50 mg) of Cr^{VI} if reduced to Cr^{III} do not interfere. 10 mg each of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pb^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Al^{III} , Pt^{IV} and U^{VI} do not interfere. Fe^{III} and Ti^{IV} are removed as insoluble hydroxide after leaching the fused alkaline melt of soil/rock samples with water prior to the determination of V. Fe^{III} may also be masked with dilute solution of potassium hydrogen phosphate. Tolerance limit of Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} is 250 and 50 μg respectively.

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Polarographic Studies of Chromate Ion in Different Media for Trace Analysis

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DETERMINATIONS of trace metals pose challenging problems which are of vital significance when present more than the prescribed limits in water and other media¹. Among them cadmium, lead, mercury and chromium excel the rest due to their high toxicity. Some of these, viz. lead and chromium are known to be insidious poisons for human

and other organisms². It is therefore desirable to monitor their concentrations in different matrices. A voltammetric method for the determination of chromium in the presence of ammonium tartrate buffer has been published previously by us³. Though, the method enables the simultaneous determination of Cd, Cr, Pb and Zn, but it requires precise control of pH and use of expensive reagents. Concerning our search for a faster, simpler and less expensive method, we tried a number of supporting electrolytes. Among them, sodium hydroxide solution proved to be the best.

Hume and Kolthoff⁴ studied polarographic behaviour of chromium in potassium cyanide medium. Sankaranarayanan *et al.*⁵ investigated electrochemical reduction of hexavalent chromium. Jindal *et al.*⁶ developed a differential pulse polarographic (dpp) method for the estimation of chromium in presence of zinc. The authors propose a routine dpp method for trace analysis of chromium in industrial effluents.

Experimental

A PAR 174-A polarographic analyser along with a drop timer was used for polarographic studies. D.C. and dp polarograms were recorded by a RE 0074 X-Y recorder. Natural drop time was employed for dc polarography. Pulse parameters in dpp were as follows: pulse amplitude, 50 mV; pulse duration, 57 ms; clock time of pulse, 1 sec. All the potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (sce). A platinum wire was used as an auxiliary electrode. A Shimadzu AA-630 atomic absorption/flame spectrophotometer was also used for sample analyses.

All chemicals used were of reagent grade. Synthetic water samples were prepared containing 0.5 ppm Pb^{II} , 1.0 ppm each of Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} and Fe^{III} with varying concentrations of Cr^{VI} (0.094–7.092 ppm). Industrial effluent samples were collected from different selected points of Basni area. The solutions were deaerated by bubbling purified nitrogen for 20 min prior to measurements.

All experiments were made in an air conditioned room at a temperature of $26 \pm 1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Polarographic reduction of Cr^{VI} was studied in ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer, phosphate buffer and sodium hydroxide medium.

Chromate ion in presence of ammonia-ammonium chloride (pH 10.0) buffer displayed a polarographic wave with a half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) of -0.28 V. It also showed dp peak at -0.30 V. This medium could not be used for quantitation purposes due to the saturation of the purge nitrogen gas with supporting electrolyte as bubbled gas depleted the solution of volatile ammonia which resulted in decreasing pH of analysing sample followed by a shift in peak potential.

NOTES

In phosphate buffer (pH 7.2), two polarographic waves were recorded in which first wave was not distinct while the second wave was observed at -1.7 V. The first wave for reduction of Cr^{VI} - Cr^{III} was not suitable for quantitative determination as its corresponding dp peak was not sharp.

A single reduction wave was obtained in $1M$ NaOH whose $E_{1/2}$ was observed at -0.78 V. The electroreduction process as indicated by log-plot analysis of d.c. wave seemed to be not exactly reversible. The influence of mercury pressure on the limiting current (I_l) at various heights (h) of the mercury column was studied. The observed linearity of I_l vs \sqrt{h} indicated that the wave was diffusion-controlled. Chromium also showed dp peak at -0.80 V. The peak height appeared proportional to the concentration of chromium in the range 0.040 – 8.112 ppm (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 The plot of calibration curve, concentration vs peak current.

Because of precise control of pH in ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer is difficult in polarographic experimental conditions and ill-defined wave of chromate in phosphate buffer, sodium hydroxide was found to be relatively better medium for the determination of micro-amounts of chromium in aqueous matrices. The method was evaluated for precision and accuracy by individual measurements of a solution containing known amount of Cr^{VI} as shown in Table 1. Chromium was also assayed over a concentration range 0.094 – 7.092 ppm in the presence of commonly occurring cations, namely Cu, Pb, Zn, Fe and Ni. Synthetic

water samples containing these ions and varying amount of chromium were analysed (Table 2). The detection limit was found to be 0.04 ppm.

TABLE 1—PRECISION AND ACCURACY OF Cr^{VI} DETERMINATION

Sample	Cr^{VI} added (ppb)	Cr^{VI} found (ppb)	Standard deviation (\pm)	Error %
Distilled water	80.00	82.10 ^a	4.8	2.6
Industrial effluent	—	90.47 ^b	6.1	—

^aAverage of five determinations. ^bAverage of four determinations.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Cr^{VI} IN SYNTHETIC WATER SAMPLES

Sample no.	Concn. of Cr^{VI} present (ppm)	Concn. of Cr^{VI} determined (ppm)	Average recovery %
1.	0.094	0.101	102
2.	0.705	0.736	
3.	1.860	1.775	
4.	3.703	3.822	
5.	5.405	5.610	
6.	7.092	6.908	

Estimation of chromium in water samples: Cr^{VI} - Cr^{III} reduction wave served as the basis for the determination of chromium employing dpp. Industrial effluent samples were digested with hydrogen peroxide to oxidise all chromium to hexavalent state. Any excess amount of hydrogen peroxide was decomposed by heating slowly on a hot plate. Finally, the samples were diluted to the desired volumes^v. The pretreated samples were taken into the polarographic cell with appropriate supporting electrolyte. The dp polarograms were subsequently recorded in the potential range of -0.3 V to -1.2 V. The peak currents were measured at -0.80 V after making blank correction. The concentration of chromium was determined by standard addition method⁶. The total number of samples thus analysed was 36. The chromium concentration in industrial effluents was found in the range 0.041 – 0.112 ppm. Atomic absorption spectroscopic method was used to compare the values obtained by dpp (Table 3).

TABLE 3—CONCENTRATION OF Cr IN INDUSTRIAL EFFLUENTS DETERMINED BY DPP AND AAS

Sample no.	Concn. of Cr (ppm)	
	DPP	AAS
1.	0.098	0.100
2.	0.031	0.090
3.	0.087	0.090
4.	0.105	0.110
Average	0.091	0.097

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Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt(II) with Ninhydrin Oxime in Presence of Pyridine

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THE most sensitive colourimetric methods for determination of cobalt are based on its reaction with compounds containing the grouping $=C(OH)-C(OH)=$. Various oximes have been reported¹ to determine cobalt spectrophotometrically. In pH 3–6 ninhydrin oxime forms a yellowish brown complex with cobalt, which by itself is not extracted into organic solvents. In presence of pyridine, the complex is extractable into chloroform. Measurement of absorbance of this extract shows a linear response with cobalt concentration. Taking advantage of this, a method has been devised to determine cobalt in micro quantities.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements were made with a Shimadzu PR1 spectrophotometer. A ECL 5651 pH-meter was used to measure the pH. A stock solution of cobalt(II) was prepared by dissolving $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (AnalaR) in distilled water. This was standardised by complexometrically using xylenol orange as indicator². Pyridine, chloroform and other organic solvents were distilled before use. Potassium hydrogen phthalate–hydrochloric acid buffer was used to adjust the pH.

Synthesis of ninhydrin oxime: To a solution of ninhydrin (2 g) dissolved in pyridine (2 ml), was added ethanolic solution (100 ml) of hydroxylaminehydrochloride (2 g) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol (80%) (Found: C, 57; H, 4.2; N, 6.8. $C_9H_7O_4N$ calcd. for: C, 56; H, 3.6; N, 7.25%).

General procedure: To an aliquot containing upto 40 μg of cobalt(II) was added 0.6% ethanolic solution (1 ml) of ninhydrin oxime followed by pyridine (0.2 ml). Buffer solution was then added

to adjust the pH to 4. The mixture was left for 1 min and the volume of the aqueous phase was made upto 10 ml. This was then equilibrated with chloroform (10 ml) for 30 s. After phase separation, the organic extract was poured over anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove water droplets. Finally the absorbance of the chloroform extract was measured at 330 nm. Amount of cobalt was computed from a previously prepared calibration curve. To test the interferences, the respective diverse ions were added to the system prior to the addition of the reagents.

Results and Discussion

The complex exhibits λ_{max} at 330 nm. The reagent itself shows high absorbance below 300 nm. However, the absorbance becomes insignificant beyond 320 nm. The complex exhibits constant and maximum absorbance when the extractions were carried out at pH 3–6. In each case, the aqueous phase after extraction was free from cobalt. The pattern of the absorption spectra of the complex extracted at pH 0–10 remains unchanged, indicating the formation of the single complex species in all cases. Apart from chloroform, other solvents like ethyl acetate, 1,2-dichloroethane, benzene and carbon tetrachloride were tested as extracting solvents. The use of ethyl acetate and 1,2-dichloroethane offered no special advantages over chloroform. Lower absorbance resulted in case of benzene. Carbon tetrachloride did not extract the complex. Apart from pyridine, some other bases were tested as auxiliary ligands. The use of β -picoline or γ -picoline did not bring about any significant change in the maximum value of absorption. In presence of α -picoline or 2,4,6-collidine, the complex is not extractable into chloroform. The nature of the extracted species is 1 : 3 (M : L) (mole ratio method).

The system conforms to Beer's law. The absorbance of the cobalt complex in chloroform shows a linear response upto 4 ppm of cobalt at 330 nm and the molar absorptivity of the complex is $1.97 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with Sandell's sensitivity $0.003 \mu g \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

Cobalt (24 μg) could be determined without interference in presence of 200-fold excess of the following ions: Fe^{III} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} , Pt^{IV} , Th^{IV} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} , U^{VI} , Sn^{II} , Cr^{III} , Hg^{II} , V^{V} , Mo^{VI} and Mn^{II} . The system tolerated less than 25-fold excess of Be^{II} , B^{III} , Cu^{I} and La^{III} . Rh^{III} interfered. The following anions did not interfere when present in 400-fold excess: ascorbate, oxalate, arsenate, bromide, iodide, fluoride, phosphate, citrate, tartrate and thiocyanate. Less than 50-fold excess of EDTA, thiosulphate and thiourea were permissible. Nitrite interfered.

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